

Quantum Resonances and Ensemble Average

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We have argued in previous notes that the free particle wavefunction $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is a complex probability used to describe interactions. As a result, quantum calculations are statistical ones and only provide part of all possible information. If an interaction only involves space, one may use $\exp(ipx)$, as in a 2-slit calculation which uses an OR probability approach to deal with probabilistic interactions with both slits (if they are about \hbar/p apart) by adding $\exp(ip \cdot r_1)$ to $\exp(ip \cdot r_2)$, where r_1 and r_2 are vectors from the center of each slit to the same point on a screen far away. The result $(\exp(ip \cdot r_1) + \exp(ip \cdot r_2)) \cdot (\exp(-ip \cdot r_1) + \exp(-ip \cdot r_2))$ gives an ensemble result- it is a statistical calculation. A single photon or particle interferes and only goes to one point and one does not know what that point is (except that it does not go to minima points). Only by considering an ensemble can one give meaning to the idea that there is a certain probability for the single photon to move to one peak versus another. In short, one performs a statistical calculation and needs to interpret it as such, we argue.

For a single particle bound state, one again has an ensemble average because an $\exp(ipx)$ interacts with $V(x)$ in a statistical manner. One creates an ensemble average to find average kinetic energy: $\{1/2m \sum_p a(p) p^2 / \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)\}$. Again, this is a statistical result. For the overall bound state, $\exp(-iE_{\text{average}}t + iPx)$ where $P=0$ deals with ensemble averages and must be considered in a statistical sense. Also, this calculation involves the particle moving in and out of the bound region and so seems to be a clear large N ensemble calculation. Furthermore, there is information lost in this calculation which one should be aware of. For high energy levels, the particle should be moving first forwards, then backwards, and this is not shown. That does not mean that it does not occur. A statistical calculation does not need to show all information and one sometimes has to obtain this extra information outside of the statistical calculation.

The reason we belabour the notion of a statistical calculation is that we believe that it also applies to the resonance decay factor $\exp(-gt)$. In textbooks (1), one often sees $\exp(-iEt)$ with $E \rightarrow E + ig$ and $\exp(-iEt) \rightarrow \exp(-iEt - gt)$. $\exp(-iEt)$ is a quantum factor which applies to a single particle and so we argue that it is a little confusing to make sense of $\exp(-gt)$ in a single particle context. In particular, one may also obtain $\exp(-gt)$ from $dN/dt = -g N(t)$, which is a statistical equation applied to radioactive decay (among other things), i.e. a large N ensemble calculation which holds for a low rate of decay. Thus $\exp(-gt)$ from $E+ig$ should be understood in terms of an ensemble calculation, we argue, which does not seem to be stressed (we suggest).

In particular, if one has some photons uniformly dispersed in an $n_1=1$ index of refraction medium (1-dimension) region of length L surrounded by $n_2 \gg n_1$, with a very small probability for refraction, $\exp(-gt)$ would need to be understood as applying to an ensemble because $\exp(-gt)$ is continuous and photons refract (leave the resonance area) in a discrete manner. Thus, $\exp(-gt)$ is a statistical solution which removes quite a bit of information. In particular, if the probability to refract is very small, $dN/dt = -1/\Delta t = N(t)^2 \text{Probability(refract)}$. The solution to this is not $\exp(-gt)$. Rather at $t=0$, $N(0) = N$. Then one may find a Δt for which, on average (ensemble average) one photon has been lost. Then $N(\Delta t) = N(0) - 1$ and one may find the

delta t2 etc. This approach uses the quantum calculated Probability(refraction), but not $\exp(-gt)$ even though this example should be a resonance. As a result, we suggest that quantum calculations are statistical in nature and as such leave out information as they describe an ensemble. In some cases, as in the reflection-refraction case, one may obtain a more detailed description of what happens than given by the resonance factor $\exp(-gt)$ which one sees in textbooks and in the Gamow factor calculation etc.

$\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ As a Complex Probability

We have argued in previous notes that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is a complex probability and so obeys traditional AND (multiply) and OR (add) operations. Furthermore, it may be normalized to 1 in the case of many possible p values. We stress that $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ is a probability because this implies that calculations using $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$ are statistical ones (over ensembles) and must be interpreted in such a manner. We also argue that statistical (average) calculations leave out information and that one should be aware of this lost information. In some cases, one cannot do better because $\exp(ipx)$ is statistical in nature and indicates that momentum hits occur with different probabilities within the wavelength \hbar/p . There does not seem to be a theory which can improve on this and give more information. We argue, however, that although this statistical loss of information in quantum mechanics often cannot be remedied, there is a case of which it can, namely that of a quantum resonance. We first, however, present two examples which demonstrate the statistical nature of a quantum calculation and its link to an ensemble. The first calculation cannot be improved upon, but for high energy levels, we argue that the second can, we argue.

Two-Slit Interference

Given the probabilistic nature of the x position of a momentum hit, described by $\exp(ipx)$, two slits about \hbar/p apart both statistically interact with such a particle. This suggests an OR situation i.e.

$$P(x) = \{ \exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(i p \cdot r_2) \} * \{ \exp(i p \cdot r_1) + \exp(i p \cdot r_2) \} \quad ((1))$$

Here x is the intensity on a screen lying on the x axis very far away from the slits and r_1, r_2 are vectors from the center of each slit to the same point on the screen.

((1)) is an ensemble average result. For a single photon or particle, one does not know where it will hit the screen. It will not appear at the minimum positions, but it is only by using that notion of an ensemble that one may give probability weights to different peak positions. Thus, ((1)) is a statistical calculation and given the inherent probability in $\exp(ipx)$, it does not seem that one may improve on it. $\exp(-iEt)$ is not involved in the interaction.

Single Particle Bound State

A single particle bound state involves a quantum calculation using the Schrodinger equation which treats the problem as a steady stream localized equilibrium. This means that particles are escaping and entering the region between the classical turning points and that this calculation is quite different from classical one. In fact, it seems that one must think in terms of an ensemble because of a single particle, it is either in the classical turning point regions or not and so the $W^*(x)W(x)$, where $W(x)$ is the wavefunction, is an ensemble calculation and must be interpreted as one, we argue.

We argue that this statistical approach based on energy conservation using an ensemble average of probabilities for kinetic energy:

$$\left\{ \sum_{p} a(p) p^2 / 2m \exp(ipx) \right\} / \left\{ \sum_{p} a(p) \exp(ipx) \right\} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((2))$$

is a statistical one and that one may actually consider information which is dropped. In particular, for high energy levels, the particle should physically be moving back and forth in 1-dimension and this is not visible in ((2)), but is visible physically. Thus, ((2)) is not the full description of the problem. It is a statistical calculation which drops the resolution of the particle direction because one solves for E_n (average) and $W(x)$, which is also an ensemble average.

Quantum Resonance

In the case of quantum resonance, one often sees textbooks (e.g. (1)) write:

$$E \rightarrow E + ig \quad \text{and} \quad \exp(-iEt) \rightarrow \exp(-iEt - gt) \quad ((3))$$

We argue that ((3)) is a result which applies to a statistical ensemble and must be interpreted in that manner. In fact, one may obtain ((3)) through a large N , low decay classical ensemble calculation:

$$dN/dt = -g N(t) \quad ((4))$$

There is no quantum mechanics in ((4)), but there is an ensemble because N is discrete while t is continuous. One cannot write $N(t) = N(t=0) \exp(-gt)$ if one has one atom. One needs an ensemble with a large N in order for this equation and result to make sense and this sense is in a statistical interpretation.

The reason we belabour this point is that $\exp(-Et)$ may apply to a single particle and in such a case it does not make sense to use $\exp(-gt)$. This factor applies to an ensemble. As long as one considers an ensemble, then $\exp(-gt)$ has a clear statistical interpretation. A statistical interpretation, however, represents one in which some information is lost. To see how information is lost, we consider the following example.

Consider a one dimensional problem in which there is a length L of vacuum with $n_1=1$ (index of refraction) surrounded by $n_2 \gg n_1$ so that there is very little refraction. We argue that this is a quantum resonance system as the probability to reflect and refract are calculated using

quantum mechanics (2) (or at least considering the electric field of the photon which we argue is equivalent to a quantum mechanical approach). Imagine that one has some photons distributed along L and moving in both directions. Then:

$$dN/dt = -1/\Delta t_1 = 2 N(t=0) \text{Probability(refract)} \quad ((5))$$

((5)) allows one to solve for t_1 , the average ensemble time it takes for one photon to refract, i.e. be lost. One does not have $\exp(-gt)$ as a solution. One then uses:

$$-1/\Delta t_2 = 2 (N(t=1) - 1) \text{Probability(refract)} \quad ((6))$$

and so on. As a result, we argue that one can do better than $\exp(-gt)$, but that $\exp(-gt)$ is a good approximation for a large ensemble with a very low probability to refract. This is well-known in statistics, but we argue that in quantum mechanical calculations, statistical notions are sometimes lost. In particular, writing $E \rightarrow E + ig$ does not really indicate why one should have a complex energy. The fact that it gives rise to $\exp(-gt)$, which is identical to a pure statistical result for a large N ensemble and low probability of escape, seems to clarify the statistical nature of the quantum calculation, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum mechanics involves statistical calculations (large N ensemble averaging) and that such calculations always lose some information. In some cases, as in a 2-slit calculation, it does not seem that one can obtain more information as $\exp(ipx)$ contains inherent probabilistic information which cannot be improved upon. In particular, a free particle with p will strike with this p in a probabilistic manner in x . As a result, one does not know with certainty at which x the p hit occurs and so for two slits, separated by about \hbar/p , one may consider probabilistic interactions with both slits and use an OR (add probability approach).

Another example is the single particle bound state which involves an ensemble average of kinetic energy in order to write a conservation of energy equation: $KE_{ave}(x) + V(x) = E$. This scenario, however, is an ensemble average of particles in the bound region (between the classical turning points) as well as particles escaping out and in in order to create a steady state scenario which does not change in time. This seems to be a clear ensemble example and we argue that there is information which is lost which one may consider. In particular, at high energy levels, the particle moves in one direction and then the other and this is not at all present in a statistical calculation which is concerned only with energy. Nevertheless, this is a physical feature that must be considered. A statistical calculation is an average result and so there may be lost information which may be recovered.

We argue that this is also the case for a quantum resonance. In textbooks, one often sees $E \rightarrow E + ig$ and $\exp(-iEt) \rightarrow \exp(-iEt -igt)$, i.e. energy becomes complex, but actually $\exp(-gt)$ follows from large N ensemble statistical considerations, i.e. $dN/dt = -g N(t)$. This large N scenario loses information, we argue, which can be recovered in certain calculations. In particular, we consider a 1-dimensional region of length L with $n_1=1$ (index of refraction) surrounded by $n_2 \gg 1$ with little probability to refract. We argue that this is a quantum resonance, (the probability to refract is

calculated quantum mechanically), but that $\exp(-gt)$ does not hold because one has: $dN/dt = -1/\Delta t_1 = N(t=0) \Delta t_1$, which yields Δt_1 , For Δt_1 , one has $-1/\Delta t_2 = (N(0)-1) \Delta t_2$ etc. Thus, $\exp(-gt)$, following from $E \rightarrow E+ig$, should be thought of in terms of a large N ensemble. We stress this point, because $\exp(-iEt)$ is often associated with a single particle and in such a case $\exp(-gt)$ does not seem to make sense.

References

1. Shankar, R. Principles of Quantum Mechanics (Plenum: 1988)
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Reflection_phase_change